

METHODS OF ENCOURAGING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article gives information about the ways and methods of encouraging students who do not have adequate motivation to learn and study something. Motivated students are much more likely to achieve their potential and find success. Motivation is an essential ingredient in effective teaching and learning. It not only yields more positive behavior in students, but it also contributes to a greater sense of wellbeing. Therefore, motivating unmotivated students plays an important role in education. In this article, ways and methods are given and explained, which can be used while working with demotivated students.

Introduction: Students have varying degrees of motivation to learn when they enter a class. Teachers want their students to work hard to learn the material during the lesson and to continue learning about the subject matter outside of class. As a result, we work to inspire learning in our pupils.

There may be an endless number of things a teacher can do to get students more motivated, but we focus on the hundreds of methods or so we think are most effective and practical. The approaches are based on psychological theories like social cognitive theory, psychotherapy techniques like motivational interviewing, recommendations from specialists in the field of education, and our own experiences as learners and educators.

Analysis and results : It's not always simple to get students inspired, particularly since there could be a variety of reasons why they're lacking enthusiasm. Students have to consider attending multiple lessons per day, finishing their homework on time, trying to keep friendships, and trying to mature regardless of whether they have low self-esteem, a disinterest in the topic, lack of support, or too much pressure put on them. When taken as a whole, they can be very demanding, which can make many students feel demotivated, particularly if they don't receive the right support. Here are some strategies for inspiring under motivated students to pursue the academic success they merit.

Common reasons why students may become demotivated:

Lack of self-esteem: Pupils with negative self-perceptions frequently shy away from challenges they perceive as beyond their reach. Procrastinating or giving up altogether is preferable to attempting and failing, which would make them feel even worse about themselves.

Absence of support: If students are not given the proper support and encouragement to learn, or if they do not receive it from their teachers, family, and peers, they may begin to doubt the value of education and their own aptitude for it. Therefore, people surrounding them should support with their inspirational lines.

Too much pressure: Many unmotivated pupils react poorly under pressure. Whether the strain is real or just imagined, they turn to avoidance, laziness, or procrastination to shield themselves from the discomfort that pressure causes. Pressure from their studies or family attitudes may make them not think clearly for their future too.

Methods to encourage unmotivated students:

Support in a positive way: Students turn to teachers and parents for approval and encouraging words, and they are more likely to be enthusiastic about learning if they feel that their work is valued and recognized. When it comes to inspiring students to work hard, be eager to learn, and accomplish their objectives, giving them frequent praise and acknowledging their contributions will go a long way.

Focus on your strengths: Focus on the area where your student shines. Constant failure can be very demoralizing, and when students' weaknesses are the only thing being addressed, self-esteem and drive are frequently affected. If students are successful, it can boost their confidence and make them feel as though they can achieve anything, which helps them believe in themselves.

Permit students to decide for themselves: Giving your pupils options within the classroom will make motivating them much simpler. In reality, when given the chance to take part in their own education, students value classroom activities more, which motivates them to work harder and be more eager to learn. For instance, if you want students to write a brief English essay on a poem, give them a choice of five or six suitable poems rather than just one, and let them choose which one they want to write their essay on. This gives them the freedom to choose their own course of action while still finishing the task.

Link classroom instruction to real-world situations: In the classroom, it is all too common to hear students ask, "When will I ever need this?," which not only indicates that they are not involved in the lesson but also that they lack motivation. Students will understand that what they are learning now will help them achieve their future objectives when they can make connections between classroom activities and practical situations. If one of your students wishes to be an engineer, for instance, knowing that they must have a strong grasp of algebra can help to increase their motivation. Show them how a topic is used regularly by "real" individuals to accomplish this. Students may not have ever been enthusiastic about math, but once they see how it may apply to them in their future, it can help build up their motivation to learn.

Present role models: Introducing role models who will encourage students to work harder and accomplish their goals is a fantastic way to increase motivation in the classroom. It might be as easy as showing them a motivational film that speaks directly to their goals or as complex as hosting Q&A meetings with kids or parents who have fascinating professions. You might even serve as your own example!

Present incentives: Small rewards encourage students to work hard and make learning enjoyable. Rewards for hard workers can include basic things like a unique break privilege or recognition points that add up to larger prizes. Students are motivated to work towards an objective by rewards, which give them a sense of accomplishment.

Concentrate on the Benefits: “The moment you doubt whether you can fly, you cease for ever to be able to do it.”— J.M. Barrie, Peter Panetta.¹

Students must have confidence in their ability to achieve. The instructor can convince students of “the concept of success” if they take baby steps. Many students had no idea that this was even possible. Like Peter Pan, a teacher must instill in their students the belief that success is attainable before equipping them with the abilities to achieve it. Success is more likely to persist in people who experience it earlier in life.

Unmotivated student is unlikely to learn much at school: But there’s a wide range of opinion on what parents and teachers can do to instill that motivation. Some swear by rewards and prizes. Others lavish praise or dole it out judiciously.

A team of Canadian and Australian researchers decided to take a scientific approach and comb through classroom studies across the world on sparking student motivation. They found 144 studies involving nearly 80,000 students, from elementary school through university.

Two conclusions jumped out. First, teachers are far more influential than parents in motivating students to learn. “If you want your students to be motivated at school, parents are important but they’re not enough,” said Julien Bureau², associate professor at Université Laval in Quebec and lead author of the study. “The teacher has more tools to work with for student motivation.” The second conclusion is about how to foster the kind of internal or intrinsic motivation that really helps children and young adults succeed in school. The way that teachers and parents influence motivation is an indirect one, by satisfying three psychological needs, according to a theory that Bureau explained to me. The three needs are competency, belonging and autonomy. In Bureau’s analysis of the nearly 150 underlying studies, a sense of competence rose to the top for helping kids feel motivated to learn. (By contrast, a sense of autonomy was more important for feeling motivated on the job.) A feeling of competence doesn’t mean that students already know how to do something but that they have confidence that they’re capable of learning it. Students who have a strong sense of competence are likely to think that they’ll get better grades if they study or they’ll succeed if they do an exercise.

Conclusions and suggestions

Reconnecting students with their schooling can be done in a variety of ways. Continue to support them. The best approach is to brainstorm strategies with other instructors that might

¹ J.M. Barrie, Peter Panetta. —“The moment you doubt whether you can fly, you cease for ever to be able to do it.”

² Julien Bureau. A self-determination theory perspective on RIASEC occupational themes: Motivation types as predictors of self-efficacy and college program domain. *Motivation Science*.

be used and might be effective with those specific students. There is no one technique that works on all students because they are all unique.

Teachers should experience methods which suit their personality, their topic, their students and their setting to increase their motivational impact. If carefully chosen, even one extra strategy could have a positive impact on students' motivation.

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